

ence of cysts will therefore likely be continually exposed to invading juveniles.

The suppression of emerging seedlings and reduced leaf weight, root weight, and tiller number of susceptible upland rice in the presence of *H. sacchari* would likely affect the crop's ability to cope with additional stresses such as weeds and drought, thereby exacerbating potential losses.

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Effect of *H. sacchari* inoculation density at sowing on mean height of rice cv. IDSA6 at 7 and 14 d after sowing (DAS), and root and leaf fresh weights at 40 DAS.

Initial inoculation density seed ⁻¹	Height (mm)		Fresh weight (g)	
	7 DAS	14 DAS	Root	Leaf
0	40.6	175	0.25	0.36
10	51.0	220	0.35	0.51
20	46.9	212	0.35	0.48
40	50.4	210	0.27	0.43
80	38.9	187	0.28	0.43
100	43.8	214	0.28	0.41
200	44.2	180	0.26	0.33
400	41.0	185	0.25	0.36
800	27.9	132	0.14	0.22
LSD ($P < 0.05$)	10.7	37.8	ns	0.16
($P < 0.01$)	14.3	50.3	-	ns
($P < 0.001$)	ns	65.4	-	-

Relationship between fresh leaf weight of IDSA6 at 90 d after sowing and *H. sacchari* population density under field conditions in sandy soil.

Usefulness of blast resistance genes and their combinations in different blast-endemic locations in India

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Identification of functional blast (caused by *Pyricularia grisea*) resistance genes for a particular region is a prerequisite for their meaningful deployment. In a mini-network program, we evaluated some blast resistance genes in six blast-endemic locations

spread over five different states in India (Cuttack in Orissa, Jagadapur and Ambikapur in Madhya Pradesh, Almora in Uttar Pradesh, Jorhat in Assam, and Suttur in Karnataka). Plants were raised from seeds sown thickly (650–700 seeds m⁻²)

under Uniform Blast Nursery conditions during the 1998 wet season.

Local susceptible cultivars—Karuna (Cuttack), HR12 (Jagadapur, Ambikapur, Almora and Suttur), and Mahsuri (Jorhat)—were used in spreader rows. A single row

of the susceptible check was planted alternately between two rows of the test entry, providing a spreader row on either side of each test entry in addition to two spreader rows around the bed. The rows were not replicated because the plant population in each row was very high for a qualitative assessment of the disease.

Uniform incidence of leaf blast occurred in all test locations at the seedling stage. Leaf blast reaction was recorded at 30 and 45 d after sowing (DAS). Results in the table are those from the second observation, when the disease was at its peak. The disease was scored using a 0–5 scale (0 = no visual symptoms; 1 = brown specks smaller than 0.5 mm in diameter; 2 = brown specks about 0.5–1 mm in diameter; 3 = roundish to elliptical lesions

about 1–3 mm in diameter with gray centers and brown margins; 4 = typical spindle-shaped blast lesions, 3 mm or longer with little or no coalescence of lesions; 5 = same as 4 but half of one more leaf killed by coalescence of lesions) (Mackill and Bonman 1992). Plants rated 1–3 were considered resistant, and those rated 4–5 were considered susceptible.

The susceptible checks—Karuna, HR12, and Mahsuri—and the two recurrent parents—Kalinga III and Vandana (being used at CRRRI for improving blast resistance)—were highly susceptible to blast in all locations (see table). Another susceptible cultivar, Co 39, carrying resistance gene *Pi-a*, (Co 39 gene) in whose background the near-isogenic lines with blast resistance genes have been developed,

succumbed to the disease in all test locations except at Jorhat, where it was resistant.

The effectiveness of individual resistance genes varied between locations. *Pi 1(t)* was effective in Jorhat, Ambikapur, and Suttur and *Pi 2(t)* in Jorhat, while *Pi 3(t)*, *Pi 4a(t)*, and *Pi 4b(t)* were generally not effective in all test locations. The resistance of F-124-1, presumably carrying *Pi 4a(t)*, however, varied in different locations. In all probability, this line might carry some additional resistance genes. Cultivar Moroberekan, which possesses many resistance genes, was resistant in five of six locations. Among recombinant inbred lines (RILs) derived from Moroberekan and Co39, however, RIL 10 [*Pi 12(t)*] showed resistance only in Suttur and RIL 29 [*Pi*

Reaction (0–5 scale) of a set of cultivars/lines possessing known genes with resistance to blast at six different locations in India.^a

Cultivar/line	Known resistance gene	Locations					
		Cuttack	Jagadapur	Ambikapur	Almora	Jorhat	Suttur
Kalinga III	nd	5	4	5	5	2	4
Vandana	nd	5	4	5	5	3	5
Co 39	<i>Pi-a</i> (Co 39 gene)	5	5	5	5	2	5
Moroberekan	<i>Pi 5(t)</i> , <i>Pi 7(t)</i> , <i>Pi 10(t)</i> , <i>Pi 12(t)</i> , <i>Pi 157(t)</i>	2	2	2	4	1	1
<i>O. minuta</i> derivative (WHD-IS-75-1-127)	<i>Pi 9(t)</i>	1	3	1	4	1	4
C101LAC	<i>Pi 1(t)</i>	5	2	1	5	1	1
C101A51	<i>Pi 2(t)</i>	5	3	2	4	3	4
C101PKT	<i>Pi 4a(t)</i> [<i>Pi-ta</i>]	5	5	5	4	4	5
C102PKT	<i>Pi 4a(t)</i> [<i>Pi-ta</i>]	4	4	5	5	3	4
C104PKT	<i>Pi 3(t)</i>	5	5	5	5	5	5
C105-TTP-4-L23	<i>Pi 4b(t)</i>	5	5	5	5	5	3
C103TTP	nd	4	3	5	5	2	2
C104LAC	nd	3	3	5	5	2	4
C101TTP-1	nd	4	5	5	4	4	4
Li-jiang-xin-tuan hei-gu	nd	5	5	5	5	5	5
F-80-1	<i>Pi k</i>	5	5	5	5	5	1
F-98-7	<i>Pi k^m</i>	5	4	5	5	3	1
F-124-1	<i>Pi-ta</i>	5	3	3	5	1	1
F-128-1	<i>Pi-ta²</i>	5	4	4	3	1	5
F-129-1	<i>Pi k^p</i>	5	5	4	5	4	3
F-145-2	<i>Pi b</i>	5	4	4	5	3	1
RIL 10	<i>Pi 12(t)</i>	4	5	4	5	5	1
RIL 29	<i>Pi 7(t)</i>	4	5	ng	5	5	5
RIL 45	<i>Pi 5(t)</i>	1	3	4	5	1	5
RIL 77	<i>Pi 5(t)</i>	5	5	5	5	5	5
RIL 249	<i>Pi 5(t)</i>	3	4	2	3	1	1
BL 122	<i>Pi 1(t)</i> , <i>Pi 2(t)</i>	1	3	1	2	1	4
BL 142	<i>Pi 1(t)</i> , <i>Pi 4(t)</i>	2	5	1	4	5	1
BL 245	<i>Pi 2(t)</i> , <i>Pi 4(t)</i>	1	2	1	1	3	1
IR64	<i>Pi ta²</i> , <i>Pi 20(t)</i>	1	nt	nt	nt	nt	5
Karuna	nd	5	5	5	5	3	5
HR12	nd	5	nt	5	5	nt	nt
Mahsuri	nd	5	nt	nt	nt	5	nt

^and = not detected, nt = not tested, ng = not germinated. Note: See text for rating scale.

7(*t*)] succumbed to the disease in all test locations. RIL 45 and 249, presumably carrying *Pi 5(t)*, showed differential reactions to pathogen populations at Jorhat and Suttur, while RIL 77 was susceptible at all test sites, suggesting that this RIL may not have the *Pi 5(t)* gene. LTH (Li-jiang-xin-tuan-hei-gu) near-isogenic lines that were susceptible at Cuttack varied in their reac-

tions at other locations, particularly in the eastern (Jorhat) and southern (Suttur) regions.

Of the four gene combinations evaluated, the one with *Pi 1(t)* and *Pi 4(t)* was susceptible to blast at Jagadapur, Almora, and Jorhat. The combination with *Pi 1(t)* and *Pi 2(t)* was resistant in all locations except Suttur, while that with *Pi 2(t)*

and *Pi 4(t)* was effective in all six test locations. Our results clearly showed the usefulness of resistance genes in different locations.

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Usefulness of combinations of bacterial blight resistance genes at Cuttack, Orissa, India

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Although 19 bacterial blight resistance genes have been identified so far (Kinoshita 1991), precise information on their compatibility or incompatibility with local pathogen populations is essential for designing breeding programs for resistant varieties. We evaluated the effectiveness of known bacterial blight resistance genes singly and in combination under field conditions against local populations of the pathogen in a trap nursery under irrigated conditions during the 1998 wet season.

Twenty near-isogenic lines in the IR24 background, 11 of them carrying single known resistance genes and the remaining nine possessing various combinations of these genes, along with an *Oryza minuta* derivative line (WHD-IS-78-1-5) and Malagkit Sungsong were tested (see table). IR24 and Karuna (Co 33) were included as susceptible checks. For each entry, 44 hills were planted per row, with 20-cm spacing between plants and rows. Two replications were maintained in a completely randomized design. Each replication consisting of four rows of the test entries was flanked on either side with a single row of the local susceptible check Karuna. Fertilizer was applied to supply 80 kg N ha⁻¹, half basally and half at the pre-tillering stage. No pesticide was applied. The fields were kept clean by hand-weeding twice.

Plants were exposed to natural infection by bacterial blight. Bacterial blight started to appear at tillering and continued to spread vertically until the crop heading stage. Both the intensity of vertical susceptibility (denoted by multiples of S [see table] and quantitative reactions to bacte-

rial blight (based on the 0–9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice*, SES, IRRI 1996) were recorded at the milk stage. Levels 1–5 covering 1–25% of leaf blade infection are considered resistant, while levels 7–9 are considered susceptible.

Reaction of near-isogenic lines carrying bacterial blight resistance genes singly and in combination, Cuttack, Orissa, India.

Variety/line	Resistance gene	Bacterial blight reaction	
		Vertical susceptibility ^a	0–9 SES scale ^b
Karuna (local susceptible check)	nd ^c	SSSS	9
IR24 (susceptible check)	<i>Xa18</i>	SSS	9
WHD-IS-78-1-5	<i>Xa23</i>	R	5
WHD-IS-78-1-5 (<i>O. minuta</i> derivative)	<i>Xa23</i>	R	5
Malagkit Sungsong	<i>Xa3</i>	R	5
IRBB1	<i>Xa1</i>	SSS	7
IRBB3	<i>Xa3</i>	SSS	7
IRBB4	<i>Xa4</i>	SSS	7
IRBB5	<i>xa5</i>	R	5
IRBB7	<i>Xa7</i>	SSS	7
IRBB8	<i>xa8</i>	R	3
IRBB10	<i>Xa10</i>	SSS	7
IRBB11	<i>Xa11</i>	SSS	7
IRBB13	<i>xa13</i>	R	5
IRBB14	<i>Xa14</i>	SSS	7
IRBB21	<i>Xa21</i>	R	1
AY4 + 5-2	<i>Xa4</i> + <i>xa5</i>	R	3
NH8-15-1-5	<i>Xa4</i> + <i>xa13</i>	R	3
NH9-52-1-4	<i>Xa4</i> + <i>Xa21</i>	R	1
NH11-21-1-3	<i>xa5</i> + <i>xa13</i>	R	1
NH12-17-2-4	<i>xa5</i> + <i>Xa21</i>	R	1
NH15-51-1-3	<i>xa13</i> + <i>Xa21</i>	R	1
NH21-37-1-1	<i>Xa4</i> + <i>xa5</i> + <i>xa13</i>	R	3
NH24-10-1-3	<i>Xa4</i> + <i>xa5</i> + <i>Xa21</i>	R	1
NH56-1-44-4	<i>Xa4</i> + <i>xa5</i> + <i>xa13</i> + <i>Xa21</i>	R	1

^aDenotes intensity of vertical susceptibility of plants (susceptible reaction of 7 restricted to 1/4 (S), 1/2 (SS), 3/4 (SSS), almost all leaves infected (SSSS); reactions of less than 7 are considered as resistant (R)). ^b0–9 scale (SES) for field test, lesion area: 1, 1–5%; 3, 6–12%; 5, 13–25%; 7, 26–50%; 9, 51–100% (reactions of 1–5 are considered as resistant, while 7 and above are susceptible). ^cnd = not detected.